

1 URINARY LEVELS OF SIRTUIN-1 ASSOCIATED WITH DISEASE ACTIVITY
2 IN LUPUS NEPHRITIS

3 Abbreviated title: *Urinary SIRT1 expression in lupus nephritis*

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32 ABSTRACT

33 Identifying new markers of disease flares in lupus nephritis (LN) that facilitate
34 patient stratification and prognosis is important. Therefore, the aim of this study
35 was to analyze whether urinary SIRT1 expression was altered in LN and
36 whether SIRT1 values in urine could be valuable biomarker of disease activity.

37 In a cohort study, urinary pellets from 40 patients diagnosed with systemic lupus
38 erythematosus (SLE) were analyzed. Clinical measures of lupus activity were
39 assessed. The expression of SIRT1 was quantified by quantitative PCR (qRT-
40 PCR) and immunoblot, then compared between patients with active lupus
41 nephritis, in remission and healthy controls. Association with lupus activity and
42 renal histological features was also analyzed. A significant increase of SIRT1
43 mRNA levels in patients with active LN were observed compared to those in
44 remission ($p = 0.02$) or healthy controls ($p = 0.009$). In addition, SIRT-1 protein
45 levels were also augmented in LN group than remission ($p = 0.029$) and
46 controls ($p = 0.001$). A strong association was found between SIRT1 expression
47 with anti-dsDNA in SLE and in patients with LN. In addition, histological features
48 in LN biopsies were related with SIRT1, increasing its expression in proliferative
49 forms. Finally, SIRT1 expression values showed a strong discriminatory power
50 of renal injury in SLE. Our study demonstrated an altered urinary expression of
51 SIRT1 and a strong association with disease activity in LN patients, being a
52 valuable marker of renal injury. These results showed the role of the SIRT1
53 pathway in the SLE pathogenesis.

54 Key words: sirtuin1; messenger RNA; inflammation; urine; systemic lupus
55 erythematosus; lupus nephritis.

56

57 ABBREVIATIONS

58 8-oxo-dG = 8-Oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine

59 anti-dsDNA = anti double strand DNA

60 AUC = area under the curve

61 FOXO1 = forkhead box protein O1

62 LN = Lupus nephritis

63 OGG1 = 8-Oxoguanine glycosylase 1

64 qRT-PCR = Quantitative Retrotranscription Polymerase Chain Reaction

65 ROC = receiver operating characteristic curve

66 SIRT1 = Sirtuin - 1

67 SLE = Systemic lupus erythematosus

68 SLEDAI = Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Disease Activity Index

69

70 INTRODUCTION

71 Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a severe chronic autoimmune disease
72 that affects multiple organ systems including the skin, heart, brain, and kidney
73 (1). It is characterized by antibody production for a variety of self-antigens, but it
74 is specifically associated with those against anti-dsDNA (anti – double strand
75 DNA) (2). Circulating dsDNA antibodies fluctuate with disease activity and are
76 associated with severe manifestations of lupus such as glomerulonephritis (3-
77 5).

78 Although the exact mechanism of the generation of dsDNA antibodies is still
79 unknown, it is likely that extracellular DNA is one trigger for the immune
80 response against dsDNA. There is a great deal of evidence supporting the
81 concept that apoptotic debris is one major source of extracellular DNA (6-8),
82 and ROS-induced oxidative DNA damage have been suggested to play
83 important role in SLE pathogenesis (9). Under normal conditions, apoptotic cells
84 are rapidly cleared, however, this process is thought to be defective in SLE,
85 causing either an increase in cell death and/or a decrease in the rate of dead
86 cell clearance (10-12). In people with SLE various changes in genes and
87 proteins have been implicated in the defects in apoptosis, these include
88 increased levels of plasma soluble Fas and bcl-2, and polymorphisms in
89 programmed cell death 1, p53 transcription factor and Sirtuin1 (SIRT1) (13-16).
90 SIRT1 is a Class III HDACs NAD⁺-dependent protein deacetylase which can
91 modulate chromatin function through direct deacetylation of histones or can
92 interact and deacetylate transcription factors and coregulators, thereby
93 regulating target gene expression (17). Thus, SIRT1 is involved in a wide
94 variety of processes, including gene transcription, metabolism, DNA repair,

95 proliferation, cell senescence and cell survival (18,19). Modification expression
96 patterns in histone and histone modifiers (SIRT1) was observed in a lupus
97 mouse model in CD4+ T cells from SLE humans (20,21). SIRT1 knockout mice
98 showed evident immunodeficiency and resveratrol, an activator of SIRT1,
99 possesses anti-inflammatory and immune-regulatory properties in pristane-
100 induced lupus mice (22). Therefore, it is surmised that SIRT1 can protect the
101 kidney from acute injury, thereby inhibiting renal cell apoptosis, inflammation
102 and fibrosis (23,24). Although much attention has focused on the identification
103 of the cellular targets and functional networks controlled by SIRT1 in SLE, the
104 urinary expression levels (mRNA and protein) of SIRT1 and its molecule targets
105 (8-Oxoguanine glycosylase 1 (OGG1), p53 and forkhead box protein O1
106 (FOXO1)), have not been investigated.

107 Thus, there is growing recognition of the need to identify markers of disease
108 flare/remission that will facilitate patient stratification according to prognosis.
109 Several urinary biomarkers of renal lesion in SLE have been reported searching
110 for clues of potential mechanisms of lesion as well as potential markers of
111 disease activity. For example, VCAM-1, MCP1 and ICAM levels in urinary
112 sediment were correlated with LN class and lupus flares (25-28). In addition, our
113 group recently showed that protein levels of associated-podocyte molecules in
114 urinary sediment were related with proteinuria and histological features in LN
115 (29). Therefore, we investigated whether the quantification of SIRT1 expression
116 in urinary sediment could reflect the degree of activity in the renal injury of SLE.
117 The objectives of the present study were quantify mRNA and protein levels of
118 SIRT1 and its target proteins OGG1, p53 and FOXO1 in urinary sediment, and
119 to assess their association with lupus activity and renal histological features.

120

121 METHODS

122 *Study population*

123 The study included 40 patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) with or
124 without lupus nephritis (LN) (15 active LN, 10 remission LN and 15 absence of
125 LN). SLE and LN were diagnosed following the KDIGO Clinical Practice
126 Guideline for Glomerulonephritis diagnostic criteria (30), as previously reported
127 (29). In summary, the presence of active LN was considered with impaired
128 kidney function with proteinuria (> 0.5 g/day or > 1 g/day with previous
129 proteinuria) or an active urine sediment, or kidney biopsy with active
130 glomerulonephritis. Remission LN was considered when the patient decreased
131 the proteinuria levels (< 0.5 g/day) and had inactive urinary sediment with stable
132 kidney function (normal values of serum creatinine and GFR). Clinical and
133 laboratory data included, serum creatinine, serum complement C3 and C4, and
134 anti-dsDNA levels, and 24h-proteinuria. Systemic Lupus Erythematosus
135 Disease Activity Index (SLEDAI) was calculated. Glomerular filtration rate was
136 estimated by the MDRD equation. We also studied the urine from 20 healthy
137 volunteers as controls which had normal renal function, normal urinalysis, and
138 no history of urinary tract infection, renal stones, or other renal or genitourinary
139 disease. As control disease group, we have analyzed urine samples from 12
140 patients with diabetic nephropathy (DN) (mean age of 64.4 ± 9.2 and 82%
141 male). DN patients were diagnosed according to World Health Organization
142 criteria and macroalbuminuria (UAE > 300 mg/24h) was present in all the
143 cases. The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the

144 Hospital Clinico of Valencia in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki of
145 1975 as revised in 2008. All subjects have signed a written informed consent.

146

147 *Urine sample processing*

148 Fresh first morning urine samples (100 mL) were collected in sterile containers
149 and were processed within 1 h after collection. To obtain a urine cell pellet, the
150 fresh first morning urine samples (50 mL) were centrifuged at 2,250 g for 30 min
151 at 4°C. This cell pellet was washed with 1 mL of sterile phosphate-buffered
152 saline, and the supernatant was removed by centrifugation at (15,000 g) for 5
153 min at 4°C, obtaining a clean cell pellet.

154

155 *RNA isolation*

156 The isolation of total RNA from the urine cell pellet was carried out using
157 miRNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, CA, USA) reagents. A cell pellet was added to 700
158 µl of QIAzol reagent, shaken vigorously, and incubated for 5 min at room
159 temperature to promote a complete dissociation of nucleoprotein complexes.
160 After adding 140 µl of chloroform and centrifuging at 12,000 g for 15 min at 4°C,
161 the aqueous phase was collected and total RNA was precipitated using 100 %
162 ethanol. The purification of total RNA was achieved using Qiagen miRNeasy
163 spin columns according to the protocol provided by the manufacturer. The RNA
164 was then eluted from the column by adding 50 µl of RNase-free water stored at
165 -80°C until use. Total RNA concentration and purity was confirmed by an
166 A260/280 absorbance ratio, using a NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer
167 (NanoDrop Technologies, DE, USA).

168

169 *Quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR)*

170 Three hundred micrograms of total RNA was treated with DNase I (Roche,
171 Mannheim, Germany) and was reverse-transcribed to cDNA using Ready-To-
172 Go You Prime First-Strand beads (GE Healthcare, UK). The quantitative PCR
173 (qPCR) reaction was done using LC Green in Qiagen Multiplex PCR Master Mix
174 and the LightCycler 480 II real-time PCR system (Roche, Mannheim, Germany).
175 All qPCR assays were run in triplicate, including appropriate controls including
176 the non-template control. Corresponding primers were designed by the Primer3
177 program (Table 1).

178 To calculate the absolute number of copies, standard curves for each gene
179 were plotted with a quantified cDNA template during each real-time PCR
180 reaction and normalized to average mRNA values between β -actin and β -2
181 microglobulin. Concentrations were calibrated from 1.0×10^6 to 1 copy number
182 per microgram of cDNA by serial 10-fold dilutions. The mRNA values for each
183 gene analyzed were expressed as the log ratio between interest gene mRNA
184 value and the average value of housekeeping gene mRNA. Consequently, if the
185 values of the mRNA levels were significantly higher in the groups of patients
186 versus controls, the gene was considered up-regulated. In contrast, if the values
187 of mRNA levels were significantly lower in disease groups versus controls, the
188 gene was considered down-regulated. All the mRNA measurements of patients
189 and controls were performed under the same conditions and at the same time.

190

191 *Homogenization of samples, electrophoresis and western blot analysis*

192 Urinary cell pellets from 50 mL of first morning urine were lysed in RIPA lysis
193 buffer with protease inhibitor cocktail and the protein concentration was
194 determined by the Lowry method. Total cell lysate (equal to 20 µg of protein)
195 was separated by 4–12% Bis–Tris polyacrylamide gels (Invitrogen, Paisley,
196 UK). Following electrophoresis, gels were transferred to polyvinylidene fluoride
197 membranes for western blotting. After blocking all night with 1% BSA,
198 membranes were incubated for 2 h with a primary antibody: mouse monoclonal
199 anti-SIRT1 antibody (1:5,000, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) and anti-β-actin mouse
200 monoclonal antibody (1:2,000, Sigma-Aldrich) as a loading control. The bands
201 were then visualized using an acid phosphatase-conjugated secondary antibody
202 (NBT/BCIP, Sigma) substrate system. Finally, the bands were digitalized and
203 quantified by the TotalLab TL-100 (version 2008) program.

204

205 *Urinary 8-Oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine Isolation and Assay*

206 The first urine in the morning was collected in polyethylene bottles. The volume
207 of the sample was measured, and after agitation, aliquots (2 × 1 mL) of the
208 homogenized urine were kept at –80 °C until further analysis. The detection of
209 8-Oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-oxo-dG) was reported previously (31).
210 Briefly, 100 µL of 3 mol/L Tris-EDTA solution (pH 8.6) was added to 1 mL of
211 urine and vortex mixed. The solution was then applied to a Bond Elut
212 C18(OH)SPE (3 mL) column, then it was washed with water, followed by 2.5%
213 acetonitrile and 1.5% methanol in 10 mmol/L borate buffer (pH 7.9). The sample
214 was eluted with 3 mL of the same buffer and applied to a Bond Elut strong
215 cation exchange column. The 8-oxo-dG was eluted with 2 mL of
216 acetonitrile/methanol in borate buffer adjusted to pH 6.0. Then, 50:50

217 dichloromethane:propane-2-ol was added to eluent and vortex mixed. The
218 sample was then centrifuged for 10 min at 3,500 rpm. The upper aqueous layer
219 was aspirated off and was evaporated to dryness under nitrogen at 50 °C.
220 Finally, the sample was reconstituted in 1 mL of HPLC running buffer without
221 acetonitrile, and 50 µL was injected into the HPLC column.
222 A Waters 515 HPLC pump model was used to separate 8-oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-
223 deoxyguanosine. This separation was carried out using a 5-µm Spherisorb
224 ODS2 column with a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The buffer used was 50 mmol/L
225 potassium phosphate (pH 5.1) in 5% acetonitrile, and the retention time was 7.5
226 min. Electrochemical detection of the urine samples was performed using an
227 ESA Coulochem II detector equipped with a 5011 high-sensitivity analytical cell,
228 which had coulometric and amperometric electrodes linked in series. To assess
229 the optimization and accuracy of the HPLC-EC assay for the isolation and
230 detection of 8-oxo-dG, appropriate chromatograms of both samples and
231 standards were recorded at the beginning of each working day. The 8-oxo-dG
232 values were expressed as the ratio to creatinine urine concentration given in
233 nmol/mmoles.

234

235 *Statistical Analysis*

236 Clinical variables were expressed as the mean ± standard deviation, or
237 percentage. In dot graph images, horizontal lines represent the median and
238 interquartile range. The differences between each of the lupus groups and the
239 controls were calculated using the Mann–Whitney U-test for continuous
240 variables. Proportions were compared with contingency tables and the Fisher's
241 exact test (n > 5). Associations between mRNA and protein levels with clinical

242 parameters were compared using the Spearman's correlation coefficient test.
243 We constructed receiver operating characteristic curves (ROC) and calculated
244 the area under the curve (AUC) to identify the discriminative power of SIRT1
245 with SLE and LN. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The
246 statistical analyses were performed with the Statistical Package for the Social
247 Sciences (version 12.1.3 for Windows; SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA) or using
248 GraphPad Prism Software Version 6.0 (GraphPad software, La Jolla, CA).

249

250 RESULTS

251 *General Characteristics of the Study Population*

252 The baseline clinical data of the study subjects are shown in Table 2. Among
253 the 40 SLE patients, fifteen had SLE in absence of lupus nephritis (disease-
254 control group) (0.22 ± 0.15 g/day), fifteen had active lupus nephritis (proteinuria
255 2.98 ± 4.12 g/day) and ten had remission lupus nephritis (0.44 ± 0.21 g/day).
256 The active LN group had worse renal function with higher proteinuria than LN
257 patients in remission and patients without LN ($P < 0.01$), and lower GFR than
258 controls ($P < 0.01$) and those with absence of LN ($P < 0.05$). Baseline serum
259 complement C3 and C4 levels were also significantly lower in active LN patients
260 compared to those in remission LN ($P < 0.05$) and in absence of LN ($P < 0.01$).
261 The highest anti-dsDNA and SLEDAI activity index were in the active LN group.

262

263 *Oxidative stress status in urine of lupus patients*

264 We characterized oxidative stress status by measuring 8-oxo-dG, in urine
265 samples from lupus patients and compared them with healthy controls. Figure
266 1A shows the increase in the yield of urinary 8-oxo-dG in the lupus patients ($P <$

267 0.0001), with a marked difference between patients with active lupus nephritis
268 and healthy subjects (LN) (7.51 ± 0.51 vs. 3.27 ± 0.35 nmol/mmol Cr, $P <$
269 0.0001). In addition, the decrease of mRNA expression levels in the active LN
270 compared to controls were highly significant for OGG1 ($P = 0.01$) (Figure 1B),
271 indicating a reduced oxidative damage DNA repair activity in these patients.

272

273 *Urinary mRNA levels of enzymes and transcription factors involved in DNA* 274 *repair*

275 The mRNA values of the enzymes sirtuin 1 (SIRT1), p53 and forkhead box
276 protein O1 (FOXO1) transcription factors in systemic lupus erythematosus
277 (SLE) groups and controls are shown in Figure 2. SIRT1 mRNA levels were
278 significantly higher ($P = 0.0007$) (Figure 2A), p53 and FOXO1 levels were
279 significantly lower ($P = 0.01$ and $P = 0.04$, respectively) in lupus patients with
280 active LN when compared those for controls (Figure 2B and C), indicating a
281 reduced DNA repair activity in these patients. The presence of remission LN
282 (LNR) or SLE patients without LN did not show significant enzyme and
283 transcription factor mRNA changes compared to control values (Figure 2).
284 Moreover, when we compared active LN group with DN patients, a significant
285 increase was observed for SIRT1 levels, whereas significant FOXO1 was
286 decreased. No significant differences were obtained for p53 mRNA values ($p =$
287 0.073).

288

289 *Urinary protein levels of SIRT1*

290 Protein levels of SIRT1 were significantly increased in overall SLE patients
291 ($n=40$) when compared to healthy subjects (2.4-fold increase, $P = 0.0068$)

292 (Supplemental Figure S1). In addition, when comparing patient groups, the
293 highest values were presented in the active LN patients compared to controls
294 (4.0-fold increase, $P = 0.001$), SLE without LN (3.3-fold increase, $P = 0.002$)
295 and remission LN (2.3-fold increase, $P = 0.029$) (Figure 3A). Similar protein
296 levels were obtained in controls, remission LN and SLE patients without
297 glomerular disease. In addition, a significant increment was observed in active
298 LN to compare with DN group (2.8-fold increase, $P = 0.002$). Finally, we
299 observed a strong correlation between SIRT1 mRNA and protein expression
300 levels in SLE ($r = 0.564$, $P = 0.0006$) (Figure 3B), in only LN patients coefficient
301 of correlation was higher ($r = 0.573$, $P = 0.01$).

302

303 *Association between SIRT1 expression with lupus activity and histological*
304 *features in patients with LN*

305 In SLE, mRNA levels of SIRT1 had a direct positive correlation with anti-dsDNA
306 ($r = 0.591$, $P = 0.0007$) (Figure 4A), and also SIRT1 protein values ($r = 0.456$, P
307 $= 0.008$) (Figure 4B). When we analyzed the association only in LN subjects,
308 SIRT1 mRNA and protein expression showed a strong correlation with anti-
309 dsDNA ($r = 0.599$, $P = 0.01$, and $r = 0.483$, $P = 0.04$, respectively). In addition,
310 we analyzed the association between mRNA and protein values of SIRT1 with
311 the ISN/RPS 2003 classification of LN in 11 renal biopsies and found a
312 significant increase in mRNA levels in proliferative forms compared to no-
313 proliferative (Class III + IV: -1.93 ± 0.27 versus Class II + V: -2.93 ± 0.13 ($P =$
314 0.009) (Figure 5A), and in protein levels (Class III + IV: 2.2-fold increased than
315 Class II + V ($P = 0.030$) (Figure 5B).

316

317 *ROC curve analysis of urinary mRNA levels of SIRT1*

318 ROC curves were calculated to assess the power for mRNA and protein levels
319 of SIRT1 in discriminating between total SLE patients (n = 40) with controls, and
320 patients with LN (active and remission) (n = 25) compared to SLE patients
321 without LN (n=15). The mRNA levels of SIRT1 had a significant AUC (0.843
322 (0.88-1.0), $P < 0.0001$) in discriminating for the SLE patient group. In addition,
323 the SIRT1 mRNA levels were also able to discriminate between LN patients
324 from SLE group without nephritis (AUC 0.845, $P < 0.0001$). Finally, the protein
325 levels of SIRT1 also discriminated for the presence of LN (active or remission
326 LN), with an AUC of 0.732 (0.66 – 0.88, $P = 0.007$).

327

328 **DISCUSSION**

329 In the present study, we have quantify the urinary expression levels of SIRT1
330 and its target proteins involved in DNA repair molecular pathway in patients with
331 or without lupus nephritis (LN) and in healthy controls. Urinary mRNA and
332 protein levels of SIRT1 were significantly increased in patients with active lupus
333 nephritis and had a significant direct association with anti-dsDNA antibodies.
334 Moreover, SIRT1 mRNA and protein levels were associated with renal
335 histological features and discriminated patients with LN.
336 These preliminary results indicate an altered expression of urinary mRNA levels
337 of molecules involved in DNA damage repair, especially SIRT1. There is an
338 association between an altered apoptosis process, an unbalanced process of
339 both apoptosis and clearance of apoptotic material with the development of
340 kidney disease in SLE (23). Therefore, experimental and human studies have
341 analyzed the serum and intrarenal expression of apoptotic-mediated molecules

342 in several renal diseases, such as diabetic nephropathy and acute or chronic
343 kidney injury (32-34).

344 In SLE, established experimental lupus models (mouse and rat) have made it
345 possible to analyze the expression of different apoptotic pathways. In the
346 mouse-lupus model, FOXO1 expression was decrease and correlated with cell
347 proliferation in the glomerulus (35), p53 glomerular protein levels were
348 correlated with clinical variables such as urea nitrogen (36), and SIRT1
349 overexpression was observed in splenic CD4+ T cells of MRL/lpr mice (20). In
350 human LN, several authors have reported an increase of immunohistochemical
351 and mRNA values of apoptosis inducers involved in intrinsic or extrinsic
352 pathways, such as caspase-3, Bax, Bcl-2 and Fas in the glomerulus (37-39). Lu
353 et al. analyzed the intrarenal expression of TNF-like weak apoptosis (TWEAK),
354 showing a glomerular and tubulointerstitial TWEAK expression associated with
355 the activity index and the histological class of lupus nephritis (40). Nevertheless,
356 no study has been performed to quantify SIRT1 and apoptotic associated
357 transcription factors in urinary samples in humans diagnosed with LN.

358 In the present study, we observed an altered expression of SIRT1, FOXO1 and
359 p53 in urinary sediment only in active LN patients. We obtained an increase in
360 both mRNA and protein levels of SIRT1 in the presence of renal damage and a
361 decrease in the expression of its target transcription factors, p53 and FOXO1. In
362 addition, we have also observed an increase in SIRT1 compared to diabetic
363 nephropathy (DN) patients, whose levels were similar to control group. This fact
364 would indicate the specificity of augmented SIRT1 levels due to renal injury in
365 lupus patients.

366 The potential dysregulation of apoptosis present in the patients with lupus
367 nephritis could be reflected as a decrease in FOXO1 and p53 mRNA levels in
368 urinary sediment. In addition, SIRT1 transcription and protein levels were
369 increased in an attempt to modulate the diminished gene expression of its
370 targets, thus increasing SIRT1 activity. Nature has evolved a variety of
371 strategies to closely modulate the activity of SIRT1 in response to apoptotic
372 stimuli, and one system is at the transcriptional level (41). However, SLE is a
373 disease not only characterized by a dysregulation in apoptosis, but also by
374 inflammatory processes. Therefore, the increase observed in urinary SIRT1
375 could be just reflective of active inflammatory state.

376 On the other hand, significant correlations were observed between mRNA
377 levels of SIRT1 in urinary sediment with serum anti-dsDNA antibodies, a marker
378 of disease activity. Accumulating evidence suggests that anti-dsDNA antibodies
379 contribute to the pathogenesis of LN through binding to cross-reactive antigens
380 or to chromatin materials, to resident renal cells and/or extracellular matrix
381 components, thereby triggering downstream cellular activation, apoptosis and
382 fibrotic processes (42). Furthermore, previous works showed that anti-DNA
383 antibodies regulate the gene expression (CXCL1/KC, iNOS, CX3CL1...) in
384 MRL/lpr mouse glomerular mesangial cells (43-45). These facts could explain
385 the significant correlation obtained between expression of DNA repair
386 molecules and circulating anti-dsDNA levels in urinary sediment of LN patients.

387 Then, both urinary SIRT1 mRNA and protein levels were associated with the
388 severity of histological features in SLE. This was more augmented in class
389 III+IV LN than it was in class II+V, suggesting an association with glomerular

390 injury overall in proliferative forms of LN, as were previous results with other
391 modulated-apoptosis proteins (FasL, bcl-2) in LN progression (37,40).

392 For its part, it might be interesting to analyze the association of the high
393 increase of urinary mRNA expression of SIRT1 with SLE progression because
394 of the important differences found between lupus patients and the control group.
395 The ROC curve analyses also revealed the strong discriminative power of
396 SIRT1, specifically in the presence of LN. These preliminary results support the
397 quantification of mRNA and protein expression of SIRT1 and its targets as an
398 emerging non-invasive tool for assessing the degree of nephritis activity in SLE.

399 On the other hand, we analyzed the expression level of the OGG1 in urinary
400 sediment. Despite the enhanced levels of the oxidative DNA damage (high
401 urinary values of the 8-oxo-dG in lupus patients) a significant decrease in
402 mRNA OGG1 was observed in our patients with active LN. The formation of 8-
403 oxo-dG is the most common form of oxidative DNA damage (46), and in human
404 cells, 8-oxodG is repaired primarily by OGG1 (47). Previous studies, reported
405 increased 8-oxo-dG in plasma and decreased mRNA expression of OGG1 in
406 leucocytes in patients with SLE (48). Our data obtained in urine were similar,
407 indicating a reduced DNA repair activity produced by oxidative damage in these
408 patients. This result is in concordance with the decrease also observed in the
409 damage DNA repair pathway of SIRT1, reflecting in decrease of p53 and
410 FOXO1 values.

411 The present cross-sectional study should be viewed within its strengths and
412 weaknesses. First, there are two systems (activity and expression) that regulate
413 SIRT1 in response to different stimuli present in the cell, and in this work we
414 have analyzed the expression, but not the deacetylase activity of SIRT1.

415 Second, because of the limitations in the original study design, we did not test
416 expression of SIRT1 and its targets in the renal biopsy specimens that could
417 corroborate our results in urinary sediment. Third, follow-up of LN patients
418 would provide additional information about the potential association between
419 lupus flare incidence and disease remission with SIRT1 levels. Finally, the
420 different cell type composition in the urine of patients compared to healthy
421 subjects may condition the SIRT1 protein and mRNA levels. However, this
422 difference would be a consequence of the presence and progression of renal
423 injury. That notwithstanding, the objective of this study was to determine the
424 expression levels and discriminative power of DNA repair enzymes in the
425 urinary sediment of LN patients, a non-invasive technique.

426 In conclusion, our results showed a significant increase in the expression of
427 SIRT1 and a strong association with anti-dsDNA and a severity of histological
428 features in the urinary sediment of LN patients, SIRT1 being a valuable
429 discriminatory marker of lupus with renal complications. These findings suggest
430 urine as a non-invasive tool for monitoring patients with lupus, and the
431 quantification of urinary SIRT1 as an attractive candidate biomarker of LN
432 progression. Further studies involving a larger cohort are warranted to firmly
433 establish urinary SIRT1 levels as an indicator of renal damage in systemic lupus
434 erythematosus.

435

436 CLINICAL PERSPECTIVES

437 Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a severe chronic autoimmune disease
438 that affects multiple organ systems, and is characterized by periods of illness,
439 called flares, and periods of wellness, or remission. Thus, there is growing

440 recognition of the need to identify markers of disease flare/remission that will
441 facilitate patient stratification according to prognosis. This study aimed to
442 evaluate the potential relationship between SIRT1 expression levels with lupus
443 activity and renal histological features in systemic lupus erythematosus.
444 The results of the present study show that SIRT1 expression level is increased
445 in patients with lupus nephritis, and there are significantly associations between
446 serum anti-dsDNA levels and protein and mRNA SIRT1 levels in this patients.
447 Interestingly, SIRT1 expression levels were associated with renal histological
448 features and was a discriminative tool for patients with LN, indicating that SIRT1
449 pathway is an important factor in the progression of nephritis in systemic lupus
450 erythematosus.
451 These findings may be of clinical relevance because provide new mechanistic
452 insights about the pathophysiology of lupus nephritis. The interrelationship
453 between SIRT1 and lupus activity and histological features opens a new
454 research pathways regarding the progression of nephritis, with translational
455 clinical applicability from assessment of non-invasive tool and therapeutic
456 perspectives focused on SIRT1.

457

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461

462 DISCLOSURES

463 The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

464

465 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

466 DO, FJC, JR and RC equally contributed to the design of the study,
467 coordination of the research and analysis and interpretation of the data. DO,
468 JPH and RC wrote the manuscript; MJF and JR, made patient selection; DO,
469 JPH, MJF, CPS, MCT and GS performed experiments; DO, JPH and MJF made
470 analysis and interpretation of results; All authors, revised the manuscript
471 critically and approved the final version of the submitted manuscript.

472

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627

628 Figure Legends

629 Figure 1. Oxidative stress status (8-oxo-dG) (A) and mRNA levels of OGG1 (B)
630 in urine of lupus patients and controls. Horizontal lines represent the median \pm
631 SEM. Data was compared by the Mann-Whitney U-test. A gene is up-regulated
632 when its relative values are higher in the disease group than those in controls.
633 Nevertheless, if the values are lower, the gene is down-regulated. CNT,
634 controls; LN, lupus nephritis; LNR, lupus nephritis remission; SLE, systemic
635 lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis.

636 Figure 2. Comparison of mRNA levels of SIRT1 (A), p53 (B) and FOXO1 (C) in
637 urinary sediment between systemic lupus erythematosus groups and healthy
638 controls. Expression analyses were determined by real-time quantitative PCR.
639 Horizontal lines represent the median \pm SEM. Data was compared by the Mann-
640 Whitney U-test. A gene is up-regulated when its relative values are higher in the
641 disease group than those in controls. Nevertheless, if the values are lower, the
642 gene is down-regulated. CNT, controls; LN, lupus nephritis; LNR, lupus
643 nephritis remission; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis.

644 Figure 3. Quantification of protein levels of SIRT1 in urinary sediment between
645 systemic lupus erythematosus groups and healthy controls (A) and correlation
646 between SIRT1 protein values with its mRNA expression in lupus patients
647 (n=40) (B). Horizontal lines represent the median \pm SEM. Data compared by the
648 Mann-Whitney U-test. Associations were analyzed using the Spearman's
649 correlation coefficient test. CNT, controls; LN, lupus nephritis; LNR, lupus
650 nephritis remission; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis.

651 Figure 4. Significant correlations between normalized mRNA (A) and protein (B)
652 values of SIRT1 with anti-dsDNA in the urinary sediment of systemic lupus
653 erythematosus patients.

654 Figure 5. Messenger RNA and protein levels of SIRT1 with the severity of
655 histological features according to the ISN/RPS 2003 classification. Lupus
656 nephritis (LN) Class III + IV (n=6) and Class II + V (n=5).

657 Table 1. Gene-targeted primers used in this study.

Target (Gene)	Primer*	Sequence 5' → 3'	Product Size (bp)
p53	Std-curve-F	atagtgtgggtggcctatgag	23
	Std-curve-R	aagggtgaaatattctccatccag	24
	qPCR-F	ctgagggtggctctgactgtacc	23
	qPCR-R	tgttccgtcccagtagattaccac	24
SIRT1	Std-curve-F	agctgatgaaccgcttgctat	21
	Std-curve-R	ttggcatattcaccacctaacc	22
	qPCR-F	ttgttattgggtcttccctcaaa	23
	qPCR-R	aaatgcagatgaggcaaaggtt	22
OGG1	Std-curve-F	agccatcctggaagaacagg	22
	Std-curve-R	gcttgtctagggccatcagg	20
	qPCR-F	tgcagcagctacgagagtcct	21
	qPCR-R	gcttgtctagggccatcagg	20
FOXO1	Std-curve-F	tcaaggataagggtgacagcaac	23
	Std-curve-R	cctaggagatttcccgtcttg	22
	qPCR-F	ataagggtgacagcaacagctc	22
	qPCR-R	ttgagcatccaccaagaacttt	22
ACTB	Std-curve-F	gaggcatcctcacctgaagta	22
	Std-curve-R	acagcctggatagcaacgtaca	22
	qPCR-F	tggagaaaatctggcaccac	20
	qPCR-R	catgatctgggtcatcttctcg	22
B2M	Std-curve-F	ctactctctttctggcctggag	24
	Std-curve-R	aaacatggagacagcactcaaagt	24
	qPCR-F	tccagcgtactccaaagattc	21
	qPCR-R	gtcaacttcaatgtcggatgg	21

658 *Primer names reflect their use in the study. The beginning of the primer name
659 described were used to construct standard-curve (Std-curve) or to amplification
660 and qPCR measurements (qPCR). The end of the primer name shows whether
661 it is a forward (F) or reverse (R) primer. ACTB: actin-beta; B2M: beta-2-

662 microglobulin; FOXO1: forkhead box protein O1; OGG1: 8-Oxoguanine
663 glycosylase; p53: transcription factor p53; SIRT1: sirtuin 1.

664

665 Table 2. Baseline clinical data of the study subjects.

Characteristics	Active LN (n=15)	Remission LN (n=10)	SLE without LN (n=15)	Healthy controls (n=20)	DN (n = 12)
Age	36.9 ± 21.4	42.2 ± 6.6*	44.5 ± 9.3*	35.3 ± 7.0	64.4 ± 9.2**‡
Gender (male/female)	4/11	2/8	1/14	3/17	9/3
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	1.08 ± 0.50*	0.92 ± 0.42	0.75 ± 0.23†	0.72 ± 0.12	1.21 ± 0.44*
GFR (mL/min/1.73m ²)	75.3 ± 33.9*	83.8 ± 29.5*	103.0 ± 33.8	104 ± 13.8	69.9 ± 26.7*
Proteinuria (g/day)	2.98 ± 4.12	0.44 ± 0.21‡	0.22 ± 0.15‡	n.d.	0.41 ± 0.03‡
Anti-dsDNA (U/mL)	154.6 ± 128.5	138.5 ± 113.1	113.2 ± 113.3	n.d.	n.d.
C3 (mg/dL)	43.1 ± 27.9	72.1 ± 36.9†	78.5 ± 32.9‡	n.d.	n.d.
C4 (mg/dL)	5.8 ± 6.4	15.2 ± 11.2†	17.3 ± 10.1‡	n.d.	n.d.
SLEDAI	10.8 ± 4.4	8.8 ± 7.4	6.3 ± 3.9†	n.d.	n.d.
Treatment					
HCQ	18.8 %	100.0 %†	66.7 %†	-	-
Azathioprine	-	30.0 %	26.7 %	-	-
Micophenolate	31.3 %	10.0 %	-	-	-
Acenocoumarol	6.3 %	10.0 %	-	-	-
Rituximab	12.5 %	20.0 %	-	-	-
Prednisone	12.5 %	30.0 %	33.3 %	-	-
Methotrexate	-	-	6.7 %	-	-
ASA	6.3 %	10.0 %	-	-	-
SLE duration (years)	4.11	8.75	8.14	-	-

666 The data are expressed as the mean \pm SD, unless otherwise noted.
667 ACEI, angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors; Anti-dsDNA, anti-double-
668 stranded DNA; ASA, acetylsalicylic acid; C3, complement 3; C4, complement
669 4; DN, diabetic nephropathy; GFR, glomerular filtration rate; HCQ,
670 Hydroxychloroquine; LN, lupus nephritis; n.d, not determined; SLE, systemic
671 lupus erythematosus; SLEDAI, systemic lupus erythematosus activity index.
672 *p < 0.05 compared with controls. †p<0.05 compared with active lupus
673 nephritis. ‡p<0.01 compared with active lupus nephritis
674

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

A)

B)

Figure 4

Figure 5

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

TITLE: URINARY OVEREXPRESSION OF SIRTUIN-1 ASSOCIATED WITH ACTIVITY IN LUPUS NEPHRITIS

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Supplemental File 1

Supplemental Figure S1. Protein levels of SIRT1 in overall SLE patient group compared to healthy subjects. Significant increased levels of protein SIRT1 were observed in SLE patients (n=32) compared to controls (n=20). Horizontal lines represent the median. Data compared by the Mann-Whitney U-test. CNT, controls; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis.

Figure S1

